

Dynamo

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of Light by Phononic Architectures.

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D4.3: Spatio-temporal maps of optimal pillars samples

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WP4. T.4.3: Upgrade of the existing picosecond ultrasonic setup

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Dynamo Spatio-temporal maps optimal pillar samples

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4. Introduction

4.1. Executive Summary

The present document relates to the development of Deliverable 4.3: Spatio-temp. maps of optimal pillar samples.

It covers the experimental details on the acquisition of full spatio-temporal maps of the vibrational state of a phononic crystal sample, which were used to guide and determine the final design of the samples to be used in Dynamo.

4.2. Relation to Other Project Documents

The present deliverable is related to the following documents:

- Deliverable 3.2: Optimal disordered phononic crystal surface or plate based on pillars.
- Deliverable 4.2: High frequency characterization set-up.

4.3. Abbreviation List

This is the list of the acronyms that are used in the present document:

- SAW: Surface Acoustic Wave
- FoV: Field of View
- FFT: Fast Fourier Transform

4.4. Reference Documents

1. Matsuda, O. *et al.* Refraction, beam splitting and dispersion of GHz surface acoustic waves by a phononic crystal. *Photoacoustics* **30**, 100471 (2023).
2. Fang, N. *et al.* Ultrasonic metamaterials with negative modulus. *Nat. Mater.* **5**, 452–456 (2006).
3. Laude, V. Principles and properties of phononic crystal waveguides. *APL Mater.* **9**, 080701 (2021).
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5. Full spatio-temporal maps of the optimal samples based on pillars or spheres

5.1. Preface

During the past few decades, artificial structures have been widely used to manipulate the acoustic properties of a wide range of materials. It is possible, for example, to use

phononic crystals¹ or different metamaterial designs² to precisely tune the acoustic response and propagation to create waveguides, sensors, and filters³⁻⁵.

Optically based, two-dimensional, time-resolved imaging approaches for Surface Acoustic Waves (SAWs) have established as a go-to technology to both generate and detect SAWs with frequencies up to several GHz, given their relatively straightforward implementation and their benefits of non-destructive, non-invasive SAW generation and the capability to detect wave propagation with optical resolution.

In Dynamo, we aim to generate broadband SAWs that will produce a large number of unique surface displacement maps at ultra-high repetition rates. Our first approach to generate this ensemble of deformation patterns was to build a nanostructured sample by using nanometric-scale pillars or holes with sizes covering a range of 100-500 nm on a substrate of Si. Theoretical studies have shown the structures with pillars present acoustic resonances in the order of several GHz, which in turn generate spatially complex surface deformation patterns, thus being perfect candidates for wavefront modulation applications. In this first set of experiments we found out that, while these samples theoretically exhibited the expected behaviour, the SAWs generated by our system were not capable of exciting any resonances with distinguishable surface displacement fields. To tackle this, we scaled our designs to cover structures with a detail size on the order of several microns. While this change on structure scale shifts the acoustic resonances of the structures to lower frequencies, we have found that it is still possible to generate rich surface displacement maps due to the diffraction of the SAW on the micrometric structures, which seem to be complex enough to generate unique structured illumination patterns.

5.2. Nanometric structuration

Our initial design can be seen on Fig. 1. Al pillars with a height of ~ 200 nm and a diameter of ~ 320 nm is randomly distributed over a thick Si substrate (which we consider semi-infinite for theoretical calculations). The pillars are placed around a flat region (where we focus our pump beam to excite the SAWs). The distances between neighbouring pillars follow a normal distribution with a mean of ~ 320 nm. The whole sample is covered with a very thin Au layer (~ 60 nm) to facilitate the absorption of energy of the pump beam and to increase the reflected signal of the probe beams. Detailed information on gold metallization for acoustics can be found in the literature⁶.

Fig. 1. Left: Top view from one of the proposed samples. Each pillar has a height of ~ 200 nm and a diameter of ~ 320 nm, with a random separation distance between them following a normal distribution with average of ~ 320 nm. Right: Theoretical dispersion curves of the sample, showing a bending mode of the structure centered at 2.16 GHz.

While theoretical calculations show a bending mode of the structure at a frequency of about 2.16 GHz, our experiments did not show non-trivial propagation mappings (i.e., propagation modes with non-cylindrical wavefronts), even when exciting the SAWs on a small region in between the pillars. A comparison of a surface snapshot between a flat sample (without any structure) and the nanostructured surface is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Surface displacement map over a $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ region for a non-structured (left) and structured (right) sample. Both images show the surface status 1.2 ns after the arrival of the pump pulse. Two major rings can be seen (close to the center and almost outside the field-of-view), with propagation speeds corresponding to the Rayleigh wave on Si. Thinner rings are also appearing, due to dispersion on the thin Au film.

Both samples exhibit the same cylindrical wavefront propagation, and while the structured sample causes some waves to travel at different speeds (wavefronts can be seen to propagate shorter distances for a snapshot captured at the same delay with respect to the pump pulse arrival), the deformation maps still show the same spatial structure. One of the reasons behind this is that, while the structure supports resonances on the bandwidth of the system, the energy of the excited SAW may not be sufficient for sustaining long-lasting resonant vibrations in a single pillar. As a result, the whole structure is seen as a homogeneous material by the SAW. This effect can be further studied by looking at the surface evolution in a single spatial position with high temporal resolution. Fig. 3 shows the surface displacement as a function of time for a single spatial position separated $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ from the pump beam position for both the non-structured (blue curve) and structured (red curve) samples over 7.5 ns with a temporal resolution of 1 ps. Each one of the oscillations of the surface corresponds to different SAW modes propagating at different speeds. While some modes propagate at the same speed in both cases, the curve for the structured sample shows oscillations happening with a small delay with respect to the flat surface.

Due to these effects, we changed to a different approach: instead of using resonances we can obtain a non-trivial surface deformation by diffraction of the SAW through a micrometric structure on the surface. The spectrum of Rayleigh waves generated in Si is centred at a frequency of 1.9 GHz, and the spot size of our pump beam is $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ (which is half the minimum wavelength of the acoustic wave we can excite, i.e., $\sim 2.5 \text{ GHz}$ for the typical phase velocity of $\sim 5 \text{ km/s}$). This means that, in theory, it should be possible to see diffraction effects of the SAW if we structure the surface with

structures acting as scatterers which size is comparable to those acoustic wavelengths.

Fig. 3. Surface displacement over time for a flat sample (bottom curve, blue) or a sample with a nanostructured surface (top curve, red).

5.3. Micrometric structuration

The chosen samples consist of a thick substrate of Si and are structured by means of a square array of holes (pillars) with a diameter of $2.4\ \mu\text{m}$, a lattice parameter of $5\ \mu\text{m}$, and a depth (height) of $3\ \mu\text{m}$. A thin Au layer ($\sim 60\ \text{nm}$) is deposited onto the surface to enhance the efficiency of SAW generation and to improve the probe SNR on the detection system. This geometry (Fig. 4) was chosen to optimize diffraction effects, as seen by previous experiences with phononic crystals in Si¹.

Fig. 4. Sample diagrams (top) and surface image of the sample with holes (bottom). A thick substrate of Si is structured with pillars (left) or holes (right) with micrometric geometries. A thin layer of Au ($\sim 60\ \text{nm}$) is placed on top of the surface to enhance the setup performance.

The need for microstructures in Si imposes significant challenges during sample fabrication. Deep etching (up to 3 microns) is a delicate process, requiring the thickness of the resist to be comparable to the depth of etching. Moreover, during the etching procedure the resist mask tends to detach from the edges, and the profile is not strictly vertical. As documented in numerous works, achieving a purely vertical etch with resist masks is feasible but often necessitates a time-consuming optimization process.

The proposed hole and pillar samples (see Fig. 4) were initially characterized through wide-field microscopy observations. While the scatterers sizes vary, and sample roughness was less than optimal, they were sufficient for observing SAW dispersion.

5.4. Temporal analysis of the acoustic field propagation on samples with micrometric structures

In order to characterize the propagation behaviour of the SAW and to obtain the full spatio-temporal information about the out-of-plane displacements, we performed a full 3D scan (2D in space + time) of the surface, which can be seen in Fig. 5. We obtained a full movie of $110.5 \times 110.5 \mu\text{m}^2$ FoV, with a total of 100×100 px, gathering snapshots of the surface at 400 ps intervals. While, at first glance, it might seem that the SAW is just propagating without perturbation, a closer inspection yields some interesting features caused by the proposed structure. For longer times, it is possible to see a cross-pattern starting to take shape (shown in Fig. 6). These surface configurations, when

Fig. 5. Temporal evolution of the SAW propagation over a $110.5 \times 110.5 \mu\text{m}^2$ region of silicon with a thin gold coating, sampled with a resolution of 100×100 px. Smaller ripples, associated with wave dispersion, can be seen in between the pump spot position (center of the images) and the leading part of the wavefront.

illuminated with a light beam, will generate complex far-field diffraction patterns that could be used to perform imaging and/or classification tasks at very high refresh rates.

Fig. 6. SAW snapshot 6.4 ns after the pump arrival (left) and image of the sample surface (right). SAW starts showing preferred propagation distances related to the orientation of the sample structuration.

A further analysis of these phenomena can be done in the Fourier domain. By taking the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) along the time axis for each pixel in the spatial domain, full vibrational maps of the SAW evolution can be generated, which can be used to study the

Fig. 7. Snapshot images of the acoustic field at several frequencies. At low frequencies, concentric rings indicate almost isotropic SAW propagation. At higher frequencies, the waves start changing its propagation directions and cross-like patterns arise.

propagation directions of SAWs at different frequencies. We show the result of this FFT in Fig. 7. For low frequencies (between 125 MHz and 500 MHz), the SAW travels through the structure without many perturbations, and the images show concentric rings that exhibit the typical symmetry of Si samples. However, at higher frequencies, the SAWs start interacting with the structure, and the images show crossing motives oriented on the diagonals, matching the symmetry axis of the structure on the surface of the sample.

While this matched our predictions, its effects on the SAW amplitude were low, and the detail level required to see them was higher than initially expected. Even though our design consists of an array of scatterers larger than $1\ \mu\text{m}$ and with a lattice parameter of $5\ \mu\text{m}$, the displacement map contains features below $1\ \mu\text{m}$ in size. Thus, it was necessary to sample the displacement field with a finer resolution to better observe SAW propagation. We used a step size of $0.3\ \mu\text{m}$ to cover a Field-of-View (FoV) of $30 \times 30\ \mu\text{m}^2$ (a total of 150×150 px).

Fig. 8. Snapshot of the out-of-plane surface displacements for a fixed delay time between pump and probe beams (left). It is possible to see the cylindrical wavefront traveling in the radial direction, suffering from diffraction with the micrometric holes. The FoV covers a total area of $30 \times 30\ \mu\text{m}^2$, sampled with a resolution of 150×150 px. Brightfield image of the sample (right).

Fig. 8 shows a snapshot of the out-of-plane surface displacement generated by the pump $2.4\ \text{ns}$ after its arrival onto the sample. With this increased spatial resolution, it can clearly be seen that the wave propagates with a cylindrical-like wavefront, but its shape gets perturbed by the presence of the scatterers. While the system is perfectly capable of doing this sampling, there is a trade-off between sampling density and acquisition speed due to the sequential nature of our measurements (the probe beam needs to travel between different regions of the sample to gather information), which has ultimately limited the size of the FoV that we can cover with high enough spatial resolution in the experiments.

Using this finer sampling, we repeated the temporal study, which results can be seen in Fig. 9. In this case, we obtained a full movie of a $20 \times 20\ \mu\text{m}^2$ FoV with a sampling spaced $0.2\ \mu\text{m}$ (for a total of 100×100 px), gathering snapshots of the surface at $400\ \text{ps}$ intervals. Again, it is possible to see how the SAW wavefront gets spatially disturbed by the surface scatterers, generating complex patterns that change over time. About $3.6\ \text{ns}$ after the pump excitation, the SAW propagates outside the FoV under study. However, there are still vibrations occurring in this small region for almost an additional $3\ \text{ns}$, generating random displacement maps that resemble speckle patterns.

While the FoV shown here does not extend further than $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, the structuration on the surface covers a larger region where the SAW will keep propagating and suffering scattering events (as seen in the large-FoV measurements), generating complex acoustic field distributions.

Fig. 9. Temporal evolution of the out-of-plane surface displacements. The FoV covers a total surface area of $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, sampled with a resolution of $100 \times 100 \text{ px}$. Wave propagation can be seen on the frames between the pump arrival on the surface and $\sim 3.6 \text{ ns}$. At that time, the wave starts getting outside of the FoV covered by the images, and residual oscillations can be observed.

6. Conclusion

We have settled on a final design for the samples that consist of micrometric holes on a Si substrate with a thin layer of Au on the surface. This configuration exhibits complex 2D acoustic field distributions that show promising avenues for ultrafast light modulation. During our initial tests, the choice between holes and pillars did not offer substantial differences, probably due to the difficulty of exciting resonant modes of the pillars with our SAW energy levels. However, further improvements on the setup (increase of pump energy and better focalization on the sample) could make it possible to generate even more complex displacement maps by using pillars. This will be studied in parallel while working on future designs for the project (consisting of twisted configurations of scatterers instead of the relatively simple square lattices that have been tested up to now). Moreover, the samples have proved to require higher sampling ratios than initially expected, which has limited our capability to obtain large-FoV 3D measurements. While the chosen structures have shown good performance on the generation of complex displacement maps, we are already working on the implementation of an even faster 2D scanning system (based on fast steering mirrors) that should allow us to obtain 3D measurements with spatial resolutions as the ones shown here (below 1 micron), but over 4 to 5 times larger FoVs (in the hundreds of microns). Furthermore, additional work needs to be performed on the samples with nanometric pillars. While these structures present resonances on the frequency range that our experimental system can excite, it is still not clear if the generated SAWs are the best candidate for resonance excitation.